

THE IMPORTANCE OF INCLUSIVE CULTURE IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract. *The aim of the following article is to investigate the importance of inclusive culture in teaching English in schools. In today's globalized era all school pupils should learn languages perfectly in order to find their position in society. In schools where the English language is taught, it might be difficult to treat and teach students equally, if they are of different cultures. Potential problems may occur because students have different understanding, background knowledge, learning abilities and cognitive skills, as well as challenges related to comprehension, pronunciation, and vocabulary and language acquisition in general.*

Keywords: *inclusive culture, language acquisition, learning abilities, cognitive skills.*

Creating an inclusive environment will not only help those students with learning differences, it will also support those students who do not have a learning difference by making them more aware, tolerant and understanding of each other.

So what is inclusion and why is it important? It is not just about including learners with Specific Learning Differences (SpLDs). Inclusion is a basic right of everyone and its objective should be to embrace everyone regardless of race, age, gender, disability, religious and cultural beliefs and sexual orientation. When we have true inclusion, it is when we have removed all barriers, discrimination and intolerance. When implemented properly, it should make everyone feel included and supported, whichever environment they are in. Inclusion is about how we structure our schools, our classrooms and our lessons so that all our students learn and participate together. An inclusive classroom is one that creates a supportive environment for all learners, including those with learning differences, and can also challenge and engage gifted and talented learners by building a more responsive learning environment. Inclusivity also means respecting people from all backgrounds and cultures, and by teaching our students the importance of this we create a much more tolerant and understanding environment, not just in the classroom and school but also in wider society. An inclusive school or classroom can only be successful when all students feel that they are truly part of the school community. This can only happen through open, honest discussion about differences and understanding and respecting people from all abilities and backgrounds. An inclusive environment is one where everyone feels valued. Creating an inclusive environment will not only help those students with learning differences, it will also support those students who do not have a learning difference by making them more aware, tolerant and understanding of each other. In English classes there are different pupils with various understanding, background knowledge, learning abilities and cognitive skills, as well as challenges related to comprehension, pronunciation, vocabulary and language acquisition in general, affect the teaching process within multilingual language classrooms. When teaching English in such a context, a teacher should consider the experience and learning approaches of the students while choosing methods appropriate to use with all of them in order to help them understand properly, without any difficulties (Quinton, 2013). Different social backgrounds,

environment and culture influence the process of language acquisition (Bećirović, Brdarević, 2019). Pupils are different in terms of experience, methods of learning and many other factors (Guild, 1986), all of which impact the learners' behavior and their learning styles. Thus, good and professional teachers use a variety of teaching methods in order to stimulate all their students' learning. For instance, relying on stereotypes regarding one's race or ethnicity is not a proper way to create a teaching plan for students of that culture (Davis, 2013).

Usually, students with different cultural background, non-native speakers of the language spoken in that country might feel lost and unaccepted, those feelings pressuring them to push their native language aside and forcing them to consider English as their main language. In a culturally responsive classroom, it is important to celebrate varieties and help non-native speakers realise that diversity is an advantage and that it enriches the whole classroom. That is the perfect method to help students achieve fluency in English without feeling uncomfortable. Even the usage of students' native language in some materials might be very helpful in English learning (Lynch, 2015). Teachers should know how to incorporate materials related to their students' diversities into everyday classes and make them feel accepted and thus encourage students to develop a sense of identity based on their differences. Teachers are important helping students not to feel like they are on their own, but have a friend in their teacher. Various grouping strategies such as grouping students according to qualifications/programs should be done by teachers. This helps to tend to their needs, for example in the language use, grammar and language skills in English language learning. At other instances a teacher may divide students according to their abilities if the learning outcome requires that. Also group dynamics need to be taken into consideration when grouping students together. Moreover, background and a proficiency level play a central role as well when grouping students. A curriculum is quite often underestimated for its importance in teaching, but it is crucial for a good pedagogic approach to academic performances. Even the simplest curriculum is important because it defines what is chosen as the best literature, authors, and texts for students, and what is the best to use in order to help students value their own culture and history (Davis, 2013)

The issue of handling how to create inclusive culture environment is a very popular topic for many researchers. We investigated all the pros and cons of having students of cultural and other diversities inside a classroom and how it influences their educational progress, their mental health, their cognitive development, as well as their socialization and relationship with peers and teachers. To start with, Witsel (2003) explained that learning and studying are not easy even in the classroom where all students are of the same culture, leading to the conclusion that the fact that students who do not belong to the same culture as their classmates have twice as more difficulties in school. With respect to the existing differences within classrooms, Bećirović (2017) indicated that younger students achieve more, thus are more motivated than older students, or that females achieve more than male students.

Regarding other researchers who dealt with the matter of immigrant studies and their coping with their background, Saenz (1994) implies that they might not suffer so much from being alone in the class with no other peers coming from the same culture, while Steele and Aronson (1995) suggest they suffer less from being marked with stereotypes connected to the culture they have grown up in. This is because of the growth of the number of relative students in one classroom, which was shown by the research of Sekaquaptewa and Thompson (2002).

Students that come from other surroundings might also feel more powerful and confident, and less visible or noticed in a classroom environment which is culturally diverse, and this encourages students of different cultures to work together and become acquainted with other cultures (Yaman & Bećirović, 2016). However, unfortunately not many teachers are able to pay extra attention to culturally diverse students, and are not even certain if they should. This is one of the questions this research is most focused on. According to Gay (1994) teachers believe their thinking and opinions are right and their facts are correct, that they are universally accepted, without considering that their own norms, values and behaviour influences their teaching and the treatment of students. As Pena (1994) indicated, teachers spend little to no time with their students and that is the main reason why teachers are not fully aware of the students' needs, and in culturally diverse classrooms this plays a crucial role. Sleeter (2001) agrees that one of the main problems is the fact that students who are usually the minority are more endangered than the ones who are numerous in the classroom and psychologically, they feel uncomfortable from the very beginning, being aware that they belong to a small group of people. It is very important, in each case, to have a proper approach with these students and to make them feel comfortable. One of the most important things would definitely be using the native language. However, while researchers like Genessee (2012) would agree that using the native language in an English classroom is more of an asset than a barrier, culturally diverse students would disagree.

Corbet (2003) explained that multilingualism in an English classroom matters and it should be fun, where students of different cultures can interact and share their interests regarding one topic. Helot and Young (2006) conducted research in which they found out that teachers become more effective when they are aware of the richness which multilingual classrooms offer, because it is there that the teacher has a large variety of possibilities in the organisation of strategies and managing the classroom. Multi-culturalism and multi ethnicity, as well as multiracial elements are incredibly important for the whole process of inclusion in school and that is why teachers should nourish and work on accepting diversities (Bećirović, 2012). Cooperative learning and social interaction solve problems such as inappropriate behaviour and lack of participation (Sechele, 2002). However, it seems that in most learning environments teachers still need much support in addressing the issue successfully.

This study found that the student's ethnical and cultural background played an important role in their overall learning experience. An important role concerning students of diverse cultures has the teacher. The results are in line with the results of McCombs (2001) and Newman (2002) who found that students who feel they have supportive and caring teachers are more motivated to engage in academic work than students with unsupportive and uncaring teachers. Indeed, teachers who learn more about their students' backgrounds, cultures, and experiences will feel more capable and efficient in their work as teachers and have less difficulty with their students acquiring the English language. During classroom interactions, teachers should keep the special cultural needs of their diverse student in mind, also some educators believe that all children benefit from inclusion because it creates an authentic microcosm of the society students will be participating in once they finish school (Karten, 2010; Rea, McLaughlin, & Walther-Thomas, 2002).

Most of the time students have their own purposes for learning or achieving specific goals within a class (Rizvić & Bećirović, 2017). It is very important to focus on the learning outcomes the teacher wants learners to achieve besides their individual background. Having a classroom with diverse learners is a wonderful opportunity to share knowledge and enrich the classroom and learning experience through different expertise. The 21st century skills aim that learners experience learning across curriculum, meaning that the same topic can be analysed from various perspectives.

Teachers can improve lives of their students, and they should work hard on that. They can also help in making the multicultural classroom more pleasant place to be in, by changing their approaches to learning. Being flexible is one of the most important aspects of teaching students of diverse cultures (Doyle, 2006). It is of great importance for teachers to investigate the issues of any kind inside the classroom and related to learning processes and to help students reduce the problems, to help students to improve their academic achievements and create a strong relationship with students. As values underlie every educational practice and behaviour expectations are culturally anchored, conflicts are likely to occur when cultural issues are not appropriate addressed in the classroom (Demir, 2009). That has shown to be the key to effective English language learning with students of diverse cultures. Still, studies found that minority ethnic groups often struggle in academic institutions due to language difficulties, feelings of isolation and having problems adjusting to a new cultural environment (Baumgartner & Johnson-Bailey, 2008). Especially important is that educational institutions support minority students, as well as encourage the creation of initiatives to support multiculturalism in schools.

REFERENCES

1. Bećirović, S. (2017). The Relationship between Gender, Motivation and Achievement in Learning English as a Foreign Language. *European Journal of Contemporary Education*, 6(2), 210-220.
2. Bećirović, S. (2012). The Role of Intercultural Education in Fostering Cross-Cultural Understanding. *Epiphany*, 5(1), 139-156.
3. Bećirović, S., Brdarević Čeljo, A., & Zavrl, I., (2019) Research into intercultural effectiveness in a multicultural educational milieu in Bosnia and Herzegovina, *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 32(1), 1336-1351, DOI: 10.1080/1331677X.2019.1629329
4. Böhm A., Davis D., Meares D., & Pearce D. (2002) *Global Student Mobility 2025 IDP Education Australia Limited*.
5. Sydney Corbett, J. (2003). *An intercultural approach to English language teaching*. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters.
6. Dubravac, V., Brdarević Čeljo, A., Bećirović, S. (2018). The English of Bosnia and Herzegovina. *World Englishes*, 37(4), 635-652. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/weng.12347>
7. Gay. G. (1994). *A synthesis of scholarship in multicultural education (Urban Monograph No.RI88062012)*. Oak Brook, IL. North Central Regional Educational Laboratory.
8. Genesee, D. F. (2012). *The Home Language: An English Language Learner's Most Valuable Resource*. Colorin Colorado. Retrieved from

- <https://www.colorincolorado.org/article/home-language-english-language-learners-most-valuable-resource>
9. Helot, C., & Young, A. (2006). *Imagining Multilingual Education in France: A Language and Cultural Awareness Project at Primary Level*. Retrieved from <http://christinehelot.u-strasbg.fr/wp-content/uploads/2013/02/2006-Imagining-Mult-educ-in-France.pdf>
 10. Nemeth, K. (2009). *Many languages, one classroom: Teaching dual and English language learners*. Silver Spring, MD: Gryphon House, Inc. of Personality and Social Psychology, 69, 797–811
 11. Pena, R. A. (1997). *Cultural differences and the construction of meaning: Implications for the leadership and organizational context of schools*. *Education Policy Analysis Archives*, 5(10), 1-19.
 12. Rizvić E., & Bećirović, S., (2017). *Willingness to Communicate in English as a Foreign Language in Bosnian-Herzegovinian EFL Context*, *EuropeanResearcher*, 8(3), 224-235